

Engineering Safety Requirements for Autonomous Driving with Large Language Models (Supplementary Materials)

A You

Consider the following state of the pedestrian and the ego vehicle:
The road consists of 2 lanes in each direction, and no physical road separation exists. The pedestrian is crossing the road at a constant speed of 2 km/h (perpendicular to the ego vehicle), and the speed of the ego vehicle is a constant 30 km/h.
Initial state: The ego vehicle is in front of the pedestrian, who stands on the sidewalk and is entering the road into the low-speed lane. The ego vehicle is in the high-speed lane, which is 4 meters away from the sidewalk.

Your task is to create a simple figure, to present this scenario.

ChatGPT

I've created a simple figure to present the scenario you described, with a top-down view of the road, the pedestrian crossing, and the ego vehicle in the high-speed lane.

A You

This figure is explaining a scenario from the top view. Each color represent one vehicle and its initial and final stage. Explain this scenario.

ChatGPT

The image depicts a top-down view of a traffic scenario involving lane changes and vehicle positioning on a multi-lane road.

- The black vehicle: It starts in the leftmost lane and maintains its lane throughout the depicted scenario.
- The green vehicle: It begins in the second lane from the left and appears to change lanes to the right, moving into the lane of the brown vehicle.
- The brown vehicle: This car initiates in the third lane from the left and seems to make a lane change to the right, ending up in front of the blue vehicle.
- The blue vehicle: Starts in the rightmost lane and maintains its lane throughout the scenario, ending up behind the brown vehicle after the brown vehicle changes lanes in front of it.

The scenario may be demonstrating the concept of zipper merging, where vehicles from adjacent lanes take turns merging into a single lane, although the image does not clearly show a merge point. It could also be illustrating proper lane-changing techniques or the dynamics of lane usage and traffic flow. The colors are used to distinguish the different paths and maneuvers of each vehicle from start to finish.

You

Here is an functional architecture of an autonomous vehicle. Explain the blocks in this figure and their interfaces.

ChatGPT

The image you've provided appears to be a simplified block diagram representing the functional architecture of an autonomous vehicle. Each block represents a distinct function or component, and the lines between them indicate interactions or data flow. Here's an explanation of each block and their interfaces:

- 1. Environment:** This block represents the external conditions and settings in which the autonomous vehicle operates. This includes the road, traffic, weather conditions, and any other external factors that might affect the vehicle's operation.
This figure is explaining a scenario from the top view. Each color represent one vehicle and its initial and final stage. Explain this scenario.
- 2. Laser beam:** This is likely a representation of a LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) system, which emits laser beams to measure distances to objects in the environment. It's a critical technology used in autonomous vehicles for creating a real-time, high-resolution 3D map of the vehicle's surroundings.
- 3. Autonomous Vehicle:** This is the central block representing the vehicle's overall system that processes inputs and controls the vehicle's operation. It includes sub-systems such as perception (interpreting sensor data), decision-making (planning the path and maneuvers based on the perceived environment), and control (executing the decision through vehicle control commands).
- 4. Acceleration:** This block likely represents the vehicle's powertrain control system, which manages the acceleration and speed of the vehicle. It takes commands from the autonomous vehicle's central system and translates them into physical acceleration or deceleration.
- 5. Vehicle platform:** This block represents the physical vehicle itself, including its mechanical and electronic components such as the chassis, wheels, engine, and electronic control units (ECUs).

Interfaces between the blocks indicate how they interact:

- The "Environment" to "Laser beam" interface suggests that the LiDAR system is receiving input from the environment, which it uses to detect objects and their range.
- The "Laser beam" to "Autonomous Vehicle" interface indicates that the LiDAR system is sending the processed data about the environment to the central system of the autonomous vehicle, which uses this data for navigation and obstacle avoidance.
- The "Autonomous Vehicle" to "Acceleration" interface shows that the central system sends control commands to the powertrain to adjust the vehicle's speed as needed.
- The "Acceleration" to "Vehicle platform" interface means that the powertrain control system's commands are executed by the vehicle's mechanical systems, resulting in the vehicle moving or stopping as directed.

This is a high-level view, and each of these blocks would have much more complexity in a real-world system, with multiple sensors and sub-systems working together to enable autonomous driving.

A You

Consider the following state of the pedestrian and the ego vehicle:

The road consists of 2 lanes in each direction, and no physical road separation exists.

The pedestrian is crossing the road at a constant speed of 2 km/h (perpendicular to the ego vehicle), and the speed of the ego vehicle is a constant 30 km/h.

Initial state: The pedestrian is visible to the driver from the front window, and their distance is around 7 meters. The pedestrian's location at the moment is on the sidewalk, and they are entering the road into the low-speed lane. The ego vehicle is in the low-speed lane, which is 0.3 meters away from the sidewalk.

Your task is to predict the location of the pedestrian, the ego vehicle, and if any collision may occur after one second.

ChatGPT

To predict the location of the pedestrian and the ego vehicle after one second, as well as assess the possibility of a collision, we need to calculate their positions based on their speeds and directions.

Pedestrian's Movement

- Speed: 2 km/h
- Direction: Perpendicular to the ego vehicle's direction

Ego Vehicle's Movement

- Speed: 30 km/h
- Direction: Along the road

Let's convert these speeds to meters per second (m/s) for easier calculation since the distances are given in meters.

- Speed conversion: $1 \text{ km/h} = \frac{1}{3.6} \text{ m/s}$

Pedestrian's Speed in m/s

$$2 \text{ km/h} \times \frac{1}{3.6} = \frac{2}{3.6} \text{ m/s}$$

Ego Vehicle's Speed in m/s

$$30 \text{ km/h} \times \frac{1}{3.6} = \frac{30}{3.6} \text{ m/s}$$

Now, let's calculate their positions after 1 second.

Now, let's calculate their positions after 1 second.

- **Pedestrian's initial position:** On the sidewalk, starting to enter the road.
- **Ego Vehicle's initial position:** 7 meters away from the pedestrian, moving towards them.

We will calculate how far each will move in one second and then determine their new positions and the possibility of a collision.

After converting the speeds to meters per second, we find:

- The pedestrian's speed is approximately 0.56 m/s .
- The ego vehicle's speed is approximately 8.33 m/s .

In one second:

- The pedestrian would have moved approximately 0.56 m into the road from the sidewalk.
- The ego vehicle would have moved approximately 8.33 m towards the pedestrian's initial position.

After one second:

- The pedestrian would be approximately 0.86 m from the original sidewalk position into the road (since they started entering the road).
- The ego vehicle's position relative to the pedestrian's initial position would be 1.33 m past where the pedestrian was initially visible, indicating the vehicle has moved past the initial pedestrian's position.

Given these calculations, **a collision would have occurred** before the one-second mark since the vehicle's movement towards the pedestrian's initial position surpasses the distance where the pedestrian was initially visible. This means the vehicle reaches and surpasses the pedestrian's starting point on the road within that second, suggesting the pedestrian and vehicle would intersect paths, assuming the pedestrian continued their path onto the road without stopping. [-]

You

What is the definition of scenario? explain by using examples.

ChatGPT

The term "scenario" refers to a detailed description of a hypothetical situation, used to explore or analyze the possible outcomes, strategies, or reactions in specific contexts. Scenarios are often employed in planning, decision-making, research, and storytelling to illustrate how different variables or decisions might influence the future or the outcome of events. They provide a structured way to envision possible futures or to understand complex systems by breaking them down into more manageable, conceivable parts.

Examples

- 1. Business Planning:** In business, scenarios are used to forecast future market conditions. For example, a company might create several scenarios to explore the potential impact of a new product launch. One scenario could describe a best-case situation where the product becomes a market leader, significantly boosting the company's revenue. Another scenario might consider the effects of a competitive response that could limit market penetration and growth. Through these scenarios, the company can plan strategies to maximize opportunities and mitigate risks.
- 2. Climate Change Research:** Scientists use scenarios to predict the effects of climate change. For instance, one scenario might assume that global greenhouse gas emissions continue to rise at the current rate, leading to a significant increase in global temperatures, sea level rise, and extreme weather events. Another scenario might consider the impact of global efforts to reduce emissions, showing a more moderate increase in temperatures and less severe environmental impacts. These scenarios help policymakers understand the potential consequences of their actions or inactions regarding climate policy.
- 3. Emergency Preparedness:** Emergency planners use scenarios to prepare for natural disasters, such as hurricanes, earthquakes, or floods. By creating a detailed scenario of a hurricane hitting a coastal city, they can plan evacuation routes, shelter locations, and resource distribution to ensure public safety. These scenarios are crucial for developing effective response plans that can save lives and minimize damage.
- 4. Technology Forecasting:** In the technology sector, scenarios are used to explore the future of technological advancements and their societal impacts. For example, a scenario might depict a future where autonomous vehicles have become the norm, significantly reducing traffic accidents, changing urban planning, and impacting the job market for drivers. This helps companies and governments anticipate changes and make informed decisions about investments, regulations, and policies.
- 5. Literature and Film:** In storytelling, a scenario can outline the plot of a novel or movie. For instance, a science fiction story might use a scenario where humans have colonized Mars, exploring the social, political, and environmental challenges of life on another planet. This scenario serves as the backdrop for character development, conflict, and resolution, providing a framework for the narrative.

In summary, scenarios are versatile tools used across various fields to simulate and analyze potential outcomes of different actions or events, helping individuals and organizations to plan more effectively for the future.